

Questionnaire result and Detailed proofs of theorems in Adaptive Location Privacy in LBS

1st Given Name Surname
 dept. name of organization (of Aff.)
 name of organization (of Aff.)
 City, Country
 email address or ORCID

2nd Given Name Surname
 dept. name of organization (of Aff.)
 name of organization (of Aff.)
 City, Country
 email address or ORCID

I. QUESTIONNAIRE AND VOTING RESULT

* 1. Which location granularity you can accept to provide to apps for each service?

	0m	1km	5km	10km	30km	100km	no
map navigation service	<input type="radio"/>						
ride hailing service	<input type="radio"/>						
sports and fitness service	<input type="radio"/>						
food delivery service	<input type="radio"/>						
hotel service	<input type="radio"/>						
weather service	<input type="radio"/>						
nearby life service	<input type="radio"/>						
tourism service	<input type="radio"/>						
other service	<input type="radio"/>						

Fig. 1: Part of the questions.

Fig. 2: Voting results for the precision requirement of each LBS class from the questionnaire survey.

PROOF OF THEOREM 2

We will use Fig 6 and Fig 7 for illustration. In this figure, we use P to denote the origin of the coordinate system. Without loss of generality, we assume the true location X is located

at the x-axis and its distance to P is d, i.e., the coordinate of X is $(-d, 0)$. We will use R to denote the test radius and use D to denote the precision requirement.

We first consider the case when the test fails, which is relatively straightforward. In this scenario, the TRM mechanism reverts to the PLM, which clearly satisfies ε -GI.

When the test succeeds, things become a little difficult. In this case, P will be released again. We consider test function first.

Test: For any released P, the point Y' should lie inside the test circle, of which the center is P and the radius is R. So we can calculate $Pr[A(X) = P]$ as follows, here A represents our TRM.

$$Pr[A(X) = P] = \iint_{x^2+y^2 \leq R^2} \frac{\varepsilon^2}{2\pi} e^{-\varepsilon\sqrt{(x+d)^2+y^2}} dx dy$$

It is straightforward to prove that $Pr[A(X) = P]$ decreases as d increases. That is, the farther X is away from P, the smaller $Pr[A(X) = P]$ is. Then, $\forall X' \in \{X' | dist(X, X') \leq r\}$, we have

$$\frac{Pr[A(X) = P]}{Pr[A(X') = P]} = \frac{\iint_{x^2+y^2 \leq R^2} \frac{\varepsilon^2}{2\pi} e^{-\varepsilon dist(X, (x,y))} dx dy}{\iint_{x^2+y^2 \leq R^2} \frac{\varepsilon^2}{2\pi} e^{-\varepsilon dist(X', (x,y))} dx dy} \quad (1)$$

$$\leq \frac{\iint_{x^2+y^2 \leq R^2} \frac{\varepsilon^2}{2\pi} e^{-\varepsilon\sqrt{(x+d)^2+y^2}} dx dy}{\iint_{x^2+y^2 \leq R^2} \frac{\varepsilon^2}{2\pi} e^{-\varepsilon\sqrt{(x+d+r)^2+y^2}} dx dy} \quad (2)$$

Above, obviously, the equality is achieved when $X' = (-d - r, 0)$. According to the triangle inequality that

$$\sqrt{(x+d+r)^2+y^2} - \sqrt{(x+d)^2+y^2} \leq r$$

We finally obtain that

$$\frac{Pr[A(X) = P]}{Pr[A(X') = P]} \leq e^{\varepsilon r}$$

We proved for any P, the equation above is correct. So in this case TRM satisfies ε -GI.

Test 1: We then consider test function 1. Let X'' denote the point which the point Y=P is released after applying PLM. If

Fig. 3: proof1

$dist(Y, X) \leq D$, Y will be released again. So we can calculate $Pr[A(X) = P]$ as follows, here d'' denotes $dist(X'', X)$

$$Pr[A(X) = P] = \iint_{x^2+y^2 \leq D^2} \frac{\varepsilon^2}{2\pi} e^{-\varepsilon\sqrt{(x+d'')^2+y^2}} dx dy$$

Then, $\forall X' \in \{X' | dist(X, X') \leq r\}$, let d'' denote $dist(X', X'')$, so we can calculate $Pr[A(X') = P]$ as follows

$$Pr[A(X') = P] = \iint_{x^2+y^2 \leq D^2} \frac{\varepsilon^2}{2\pi} e^{-\varepsilon\sqrt{(x+d'')^2+y^2}} dx dy$$

According to the triangle inequality that

$$\sqrt{(x+d'')^2+y^2} - \sqrt{(x+d')^2+y^2} \leq r$$

We can obtain that

$$\frac{Pr[A(X) = P]}{Pr[A(X') = P]} = \frac{\iint_{x^2+y^2 \leq R^2} \frac{\varepsilon^2}{2\pi} e^{-\varepsilon\sqrt{(x+d'')^2+y^2}} dx dy}{\iint_{x^2+y^2 \leq R^2} \frac{\varepsilon^2}{2\pi} e^{-\varepsilon\sqrt{(x+d')^2+y^2}} dx dy} \leq e^{\varepsilon r}$$

Fig. 4: proof1

In conclusion, our TRM satisfies ε -GI.

PROOF OF THEOREM 3

In this section, we will prove the claim that ε_{real} increases with d increasing. We still use P to denote the origin of coordinate system and consider a pair of points $X(-d, 0)$ and $X'(-d-r, 0)$ in this system. Here, we ensure that X and X' are symmetric about the axis of $S(W)$ to construct the auxiliary

circle (the dashed circle on the left). We first show that in TRM the value $\frac{Pr[A(X)=P]}{Pr[A(X')=P]}$ increases with d increasing, based on which the original claim becomes straightforward.

Obviously, the positions of X and X' relative to the test circle have three conditions: both are inside the circle, only X is inside and neither are inside. We first consider the first condition, which is shown in Fig. 7(a). Fig. 7(b) is generated by moving X and X' a small distance away from P , i.e., d increases. We apply $Pr_S(X)$ to denote the probability that the generated location of X applying PLM is in S . Then we can get

$$\frac{Pr[A(X) = P]}{Pr[A(X') = P]} = \frac{Pr_S(X) + Pr_T(X)}{Pr_S(X') + Pr_T(X)}$$

Fig. 5: proof1

Here, according to symmetry, we know $Pr_S(X) = Pr_S(X')$ and $Pr_T(X) > Pr_T(X')$. For fig. 7(b), we can get

$$\frac{Pr[A(X) = P]}{Pr[A(X') = P]} = \frac{Pr_W(X) + Pr_{S-W}(X) + Pr_T(X)}{Pr_W(X') + Pr_{S-W}(X') + Pr_T(X')}$$

Similarly, according to symmetry, we know $Pr_W(X) = Pr_W(X')$, and $Pr_{S-W}(X) > Pr_{S-W}(X')$, $Pr_T(X) > Pr_T(X')$. Besides, according to properties of the probability distribution function of PLM, we can get that $\forall t \in T, \frac{D_X(t)}{D_{X'}(t)} \leq \frac{D_X(t)}{D_{X'}(t)}$. The inequality holds with equality when t, X , and X' are collinear.

$$\frac{Pr_T(X)}{Pr_T(X')} > \frac{Pr_T(X)}{Pr_T(X')}$$

The equation above can be inferred. In conclusion, the following claim can be acquired:

$$\frac{Pr[A(X) = P]}{Pr[A(X') = P]} < \frac{Pr[A(X) = P]}{Pr[A(X') = P]}$$

This claim holds in the other two conditions as well and the proof is omitted. So, we come to the conclusion that as d increases, the privacy cost also increases in TRM.

Let's now turn to prove the second claim that ε_{real} decreases with R decreasing. We use Fig. 8 to illustrate our proof. In this figure, two circles corresponds two test circles in TRM with different radiuses R and R' ($R' > R$). We consider the condition that the release point is P . Obviously, according to the proof of the first-half claim, we know when the test radius is R , the real privacy cost is

$$\varepsilon_{real} = \frac{Pr_A(X) + Pr_B(X) + Pr_C(X)}{Pr_A(X') + Pr_B(X') + Pr_C(X')}$$

Fig. 6: proof3b

where according to symmetry, $Pr_A(X) = Pr_A(X')$, when test radius increases to R' , ε'_{real} is

$$\varepsilon'_{real} = \frac{Pr_{A,B,C}(X) + Pr_{B'}(X) + Pr_D(X) + Pr_E(X)}{Pr_{A,B,C}(X') + Pr_{B'}(X') + Pr_D(X') + Pr_E(X')}$$

We find that $Pr_{B'}(X) < Pr_{B'}(X')$ and $Pr_D(X) = Pr_D(X')$. Besides, it is not difficult to prove

$$1 < \frac{Pr_E(X)}{Pr_E(X')} < \frac{Pr_C(X)}{Pr_C(X')}$$

Based on these inequalities, we could obtain the original claim that $\varepsilon'_{real} < \varepsilon_{real}$, i.e., the real privacy cost decreases with R increasing.

We finally compare that the privacy cost of TRM with that of PTM proposed by Chatzikokolakis et al. [3]. It is easy to find that in the linear Laplace mechanism of [3], for the true location X , the real privacy cost ε_{real} while the test succeeds (output the prediction P) is

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{Pr[A(X) = P]}{Pr[A(X') = P]} &= \frac{\iint_{-R < x < R, y=0} e^{-\varepsilon \text{dist}(X, (x,y))} dx dy}{\iint_{-R < x < R, y=0} e^{-\varepsilon \text{dist}(X', (x,y))} dx dy} \\ &= \frac{\iint_{-R < x < R, y=0} e^{-\varepsilon \sqrt{(x+d)^2 + y^2}} dx dy}{\iint_{-R < x < R, y=0} e^{-\varepsilon \sqrt{(x+d+r)^2 + y^2}} dx dy} \end{aligned}$$

We can then compare this value with equation (3) and (4). Here, the difference is that in PTM the integrals are performed within a line segment (P is the midpoint and the length is $2R$), while in TRM, the integrals are performed within a circle (P is the center and R is the radius). It is not difficult to show that the gap of the line integrals is larger than that of the planar integrals. So we come to the conclusion that TRM with test function can further reduce the real privacy costs.

REFERENCES

- [1] Andrés, Miguel E., et al. "Geo-indistinguishability: Differential privacy for location-based systems." Proceedings of the 2013 ACM SIGSAC conference on Computer & communications security. 2013.
- [2] Liang, Yuting, and Ke Yi. "Concentrated geo-privacy." Proceedings of the 2023 ACM SIGSAC Conference on Computer and Communications Security. 2023.

- [3] Chatzikokolakis, Konstantinos, Catuscia Palamidessi, and Marco Stronati. "A predictive differentially-private mechanism for mobility traces." Privacy Enhancing Technologies: 14th International Symposium, PETS 2014, Amsterdam, The Netherlands, July 16-18, 2014. Proceedings 14. Springer International Publishing, 2014.